

ADSORPTION OF PHOSPHATE BY CLAY MINERALS PART I. KAOLINITE AND HALLOYSITE

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Adsorption of phosphate and other ions by kaolinite and halloysite, which are present in certain soil types, has been investigated. Adsorption of phosphate is appreciable, but of other ions, negligible. The results indicate that phosphate adsorption or anion exchange, in general, by kaolinite is rendered complicated by the presence of aluminium, either in the free state or present in the laterally broken down lattice of clay minerals when the latter are finely powdered. Removal of free alumina by means of dilute acid and/or treatment of phosphatised kaolinite with ammonium oxalate solution bring down the p.c.a. to its normal low value. Analysis of the oxalate leachate shows the formation of definite aluminium phosphates on phosphatisation of kaolinite. This has been further confirmed with the help of electron diffraction pictures. The agreement between the p.a.c. and b.e.c. of kaolinite has been explained by assuming that the surface OH groups act as the centre of both cation and anion exchange, depending on the experimental conditions. B.e.c. of halloysite has been found almost the same as of kaolinite, but p.a.c. is higher, particularly in acidic solution.

Soil being a heterogeneous body, the different types of constituents, which should be considered for a discussion on phosphate adsorption, are the silicate minerals, metallic oxides and organic matter. The last mentioned constituent does not play as much significant role in phosphate fixation as the others. There are two schools of thought on the subject. One regards it as a process of anion exchange and the other considers it as a chemical reaction. A review of the literature on phosphate fixation up to 1940 has been published by Midgley (*Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1940, 5, 24). Some of the important papers published later were reviewed by the author in an earlier communication (Sinha and Chowdhury, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 211). Adsorption of tartrate by soil is very small, whereas citrate is not adsorbed at all, although both displace adsorbed phosphate. Dean and Rubins (*Soil Sci.*, 1947, 63, 377) as well as Schollenberger (*ibid.*, 1947, 64, 371) noticed that arsenate and phosphate were able to replace each other in the soil. Sieling (*Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1946, 11, 161) noticed that neither phosphate nor arsenate was adsorbed by kaolinite which had been previously washed with acid to remove the free oxide, but adsorption took place when the sample was ground in a ball mill, and it was negligible when the ground sample was again washed with acid. He ascribed the adsorption of phosphate or arsenate to the formation of alumina as a result of grinding. Haseman *et al.* (*Soil Sci.*, 1950, 70, 257) who studied the reaction at 90°, using a molar solution of phosphate, observed that kaolinite was almost completely decomposed and was converted into palmerite-like products.

Most of the studies on phosphate or anion adsorption were restricted to soil or its clay fraction, and this prevented a correct appraisal of phosphate adsorption. Amongst the studies with purer minerals, there are some with kaolinites, and a very few with montmorillonites. In this respect the work of Chatterjee and Datta (*J. Soil Sci.*, 1951, 2, 224) covers a number of points. They studied the adsorption of phosphate

by H-kaolinite and H-montmorillonite under varying conditions of p_H , concentration of PO_4^{3-} and particle size. The part played by the free iron and aluminium oxides was particularly investigated and a correlation was observed between iron and alumina, brought into solution by dilute HCl at p_H 3.0, and PO_4^{3-} adsorbed at this p_H .

The present series of study has been conducted, keeping in view the heterogeneous nature of soil. Adsorption of phosphate by alumina was reported previously (Sinha and Chowdhury, *loc. cit.*). The work has also been extended to silicate minerals other than those usually present in soil. Thus, besides several kaolinites, montmorillonites and attapulgite, some micas, talc, pyrophyllite and halloysite, etc. have been included in this study. Part I deals with the results obtained with kaolinite and halloysite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Kaolinite and Halloysite.—Two different samples, KaA and KaB, of kaolinite were used. The analytical as well as X-ray data of both the samples conform to those of the pure mineral. The entire clay fraction (consisting of particles $<2\mu$) of KaA was used, but in the case of KaB, particles having e.s.d. 2–0.5 μ , which were fractionated by sedimentation, were employed. The samples were converted into their hydrogen forms. The analysis of kaolinite and halloysite* samples is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

	H ₂ O (110° to ignition).	SiO ₂ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .
KaA	13.85%	46.13%	39.62%	...
KaB	13.79	46.40	39.40	0.05%
Halloysite	17.90	43.92	38.35	...

Anion Adsorption.—The experimental procedure is the same as that used previously by Sinha and Chowdhury (*loc. cit.*, p. 213). For purposes of a comparative study the reaction, which went on very slowly after 4 or 5 days, was not usually prolonged beyond five days.

In some experiments, the adsorbed phosphate was leached out with solutions of ammonium nitrate, sulphate, oxalate, citrate or fluoride instead of NaOH or HNO₃. Before applying Pemberton's procedure for phosphorus determination, the phosphate was precipitated as ferric phosphate in the sulphate as well as in fluoride leachate after removal of fluoride; oxalate and citrate were decomposed by boiling with strong nitric acid.

Magnesium was determined either by the oxine method after separation of phosphate or according to Handy's method of titrating the $Mg(NH_4)PO_4$ with standard acid. In the absence of phosphate, Al was estimated by the oxine method.

For the determination of silica the oxalate, citrate, etc. were first decomposed by baking and ignition. Table II records the data on the adsorption of phosphate and other anions by KaA.

* Sample received from Prof. T. F. Bates, Pennsylvania (U.S.A.) to whom the author's thanks are due.

TABLE II

Adsorption of anions by KaA.

B.e.c. = 4.0 m.e.*

Solution.	Anion adsorbed (m.e./100 g.**)	Solution.	* Anion adsorbed (m.e./100 g.).
0.0125N-H ₂ PO ₄	1.2	0.05N-K ₂ SO ₄	Nil
0.02N „	2.0	0.05N-K ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ SO ₄ (pH 2.5)	„
0.05N „	4.0	0.05N-K ₂ CrO ₄	„
0.066N „	6.5	0.05N-Oxalic acid	„
N-NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄ (pH 4.0)	8.0		

* By Parker's method (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1929, 21, 1030).** Assuming that phosphorus is adsorbed as PO₄³⁻.

The results demonstrate that even the clay fraction of kaolinite adsorbs only a small amount of phosphate and does not at all take up sulphate, chromate or oxalate.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Grinding of Kaolinite on Anion Adsorption.—Grinding has been found to increase anion adsorption, particularly phosphate. Stout (*Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1939, 4, 177) suggested on the basis of X ray and chemical analysis that OH groups released by grinding reacted with H₂PO₄⁻ ions with the consequent loss of water. The characteristic X-ray diffraction of kaolinite was absent in phosphatised kaolinite but reappeared on removal of phosphate. Coleman (*Soil Sci.*, 1944, 58, 71) attributed the major proportion of phosphate, adsorbed by kaolinitic and montmorillonitic clays and other fine clays, to the free aluminium oxide and ferric oxide present as impurities (cf. Chatterjee and Datta, *loc. cit.*).

The grinding of kaolinite, whether wet or dry (Shaw, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 1032) exposes a large number of OH groups, which along the lateral plane are composed of those lying between aluminium and silicon layers. Moreover, the breaking of Si-O-Al linkages leads in the presence of moisture to Al-OH groups. Aluminium oxide definitely possesses anion exchange and phosphate adsorption capacities. It is likely therefore that the OH groups attached to Al, which are exposed either by grinding or hydrolytic cleavage, are the centres of phosphate interaction. Ordinarily, kaolinite adsorbs a small amount of phosphate (Table II) but no sulphate or chromate. The basic function of the small number of Al-OH groups present is perhaps too weak to react with sulphate or chromate ions. Grinding increases the number of anion-exchange spots and, as such, an increase of anion adsorption, more particularly of phosphate, is clearly noticeable (cf. Table III).

TABLE III

Adsorption of anions by ground kaolinite (Ka₂A).

Solution.	p_H of soln.	Adsorbed anion (m.e./100g.).	Solution.	p_H of soln.	Adsorbed anion (m.e./100g.).	Solution.	p_H of soln.	Adsorbed anion (m.e./100g.).
0.0125N-H ₃ PO ₄	2.52	102	0.05N-H ₃ PO ₄ + K ₂ HPO ₄	3.03	237	0.05N-Oxalic acid	1.75	8.7
0.025N- "	2.30	172	" " "	3.6	250	0.05N-Na-oxalate	3.0	21.7
0.05N- "	2.05	237	" " "	4.3	204	0.05N-K ₂ SO ₄ +H ₂ SO ₄	2.52	11.6
0.0125N-K ₂ HPO ₄	...	22	" " "	6.4	105	0.005N-H ₂ SO ₄	...	9.5
0.025N- "	...	25	" " "	7.1	57	0.05N-Chromic acid	...	7.9
0.05N- "	...	32	" " "	8.0	32	+K ₂ CrO ₄	4.3	7.9
						0.05N-K ₂ CrO ₄	9.0	Nil

Role of Aluminium in Anion-adsorption by Kaolinite.—A comparison of the above data with similar results obtained with Al₂O₃ sol (Table IV) clearly demonstrates the role of alumina in anion adsorption by kaolinite. Grinding as a method of increasing the surface of minerals has been variously questioned (Jackson and Truog, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1939, **4**, 136; Laws and Page, *Soil Sci.*, 1946, **62**, 319; Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, **41**, 935; Perkins, *Soil Sci.*, 1948, **65**, 185; Sieling, *loc. cit.*). The formation of different aluminium phosphates in the reaction between ground kaolinite and phosphate solutions was shown by Ensminger (*Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1948, **13**, 170).

TABLE IV

Comparison of adsorption of anions by Al₂O₃ sol and ground kaolinite.

Solution	Absorption (m.e./100 g.) by	
	Al ₂ O ₃ sol.	Ground kaolinite.
0.05N-H ₃ PO ₄	527	237
0.05N-KH ₂ PO ₄	250	105
0.05N-K ₂ HPO ₄	180	32
0.05N-H ₂ CrO ₄	21	8
0.05N-Oxalic acid	56	21.6
0.05N-K ₂ SO ₄ +H ₂ SO ₄ (p_H 2.5)	38.6	14

In order to investigate therefore the nature of complication that may arise out of this kind of interactions and to evaluate more definitely the role of aluminium in phosphate adsorption, two samples of ground H-kaolinite, weighing 3.02 g. (I) and 1.35 g. (II), were leached with about 450 ml. of 0.05 N-HCl. The leaching was evidently more drastic in the case of the smaller sample. Phosphate adsorption was studied with the original kaolinite, the two samples of ground kaolinite and two samples (I and II) of the ground and acid-treated kaolinite; simultaneously the b.e.c. was also measured. The results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V

B.e.c. and phosphate adsorption of ground kaolinite (KaB).

Material	B.e.c.	PO ₄ ³⁻ adsorbed from 0.05N- H ₃ PO ₄ .	in acid leachate		P.a.c. (m.e./100g.).
			Al ₂ O ₃ (m.e./100g.).	SiO ₂ (m.mol./100g.).	
Original *	4	4	...	...	8.2
H-Kaolinite (I) kaolinite, ground (KaB)	10	220	...	...	...
Kaolinite, ground and acid-treated	10	14	223	16	18
(II) Kaolinite, ground (KaB)	8	121	—	...	...
Kaolinite, ground and acid-treated	8	15	221	15	18.5

Ground kaolinite shows increased phosphate adsorption, which is drastically reduced when the ground kaolinite is acid-washed. In the acid leachate considerable amounts of alumina and some amount of silica have been found, indicating the part played by alumina in phosphate adsorption. Both the original and the acid-washed ground kaolinite samples possess somewhat greater b.e.c. and phosphate adsorption, owing evidently to a decrease of particle size. The presence of silica in the acid leachate is indicative of possible disintegration of the kaolinite lattice caused by grinding.

The role of alumina in phosphate adsorption by ground kaolinite also has been shown in the following way.

(i) H-kaolinite (KaB) was ground in an agate mortar in presence of *N*-NH₄H₂PO₄ solution (*p_H* 4) and after grinding for 100 hours was washed with aqueous alcohol to make it free from the adhering phosphate. The phosphate taken up by the material was then extracted with *N*-ammonium oxalate (*p_H* 5). The p.a.c. of the dephosphatised material was then determined.

(ii) In another experiment, the same H-kaolinite (KaB) was ground alone in an agate mortar and its p.a.c. was determined by the usual procedure and dephosphatised by leaching with *N*-ammonium oxalate solution (*p_H* 5). The p.a.c. of the dephosphatised material was again determined. The results of both these experiments are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

P.a.c. of ground and dephosphatised kaolinite.

Material.	P.a.c. (m.e./100 g.)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (m.e./100 g.).	Al ₂ O ₃ (m.e./100g.).	SiO ₂ (m.mol./100g.).
(f) Ground with phosphate	4	322	322	72
(#) Ground without phosphate	61	148	140	72

These experiments further suggest a possible breakdown of the mineral by grinding. The above experiments further demonstrate that the reaction with phosphate is more thorough when ground in its presence than when the ground sample is treated with the phosphate solution. Ammonium oxalate dephosphatises the ground sample by removing, more or less specifically, the aluminium phosphate that is formed*. Consequently, the p.a.c. of the dephosphatised sample is considerably reduced. The removal of alumina is almost complete in the first experiment, and hence, the p.a.c. drops to the value of the original unground sample, whereas alumina still present after dephosphatisation in the second sample accounts for its higher p.a.c.

Decomposition of the Lattice of Kaolinite by Phosphate Adsorption

Phosphatisation and subsequent removal of phosphate by ammonium oxalate solution have been shown to cause a slight breakdown of the kaolinite lattice. This is apparently due to the removal of lattice aluminium by combination with phosphate. It is not therefore unlikely that repeated phosphatisation will eventually cause a complete breakdown (Low and Black, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1947, 12, 180). The decomposition is considerably enhanced at a higher temperature. For instance, on treatment with $N-NH_4H_2PO_4$ at p_H 4, kaolinite (KaB), which adsorbed only 8.8 m.e. of phosphate at the ordinary temperature, took up nearly 600 m.e. when kept at 95° for 150 hours, the p_H of the solution being raised to 5.7 at the end of the reaction. The phosphatised material on analysis gave 14.9% moisture (105° to ignition), 35.5% SiO_2 , 38.3% Al_2O_3 and 11.2% P_2O_5 . Assuming that silica is lost as a result of the breakdown of the mineral, it is calculated that nearly 21% of kaolinite has been decomposed in this way. The ratio, $Al_2O_3 : P_2O_5 = 1 : 0.21$, corresponds to variscite, which Cole and Jackson (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 128) also observed by reacting aluminium chloride with phosphate solutions. Compositions other than variscite are, of course, not unlikely.

The use of high temperature, viz. 95° , in the determination of phosphate adsorption capacity of clay and other minerals is therefore not free from objection. This is more so in the case of kaolinite in which there is definite evidence of a chemical reaction and subsequent decomposition. That kaolinite is attacked, though very slowly, even at the ordinary temperature at low p_H , is clearly demonstrated by the data recorded in Table VII. But at p_H 7 the reaction does not seem even at the end of 6 months to proceed further than what occurs in five days.

TABLE VII
Phosphate adsorption by kaolinite over long periods of contact.

Material.	Soln. used.	Period of contact.	Phosphate adsorption (m.e./100 g.) Long period of contact.	5 days' contact.
KaA	0.18N- H_3PO_4 (p_H 4)	Over 5 years	1350	15.0
KaB	N-Ammonium phosphate (p_H 4)	9 months	333	9.0
KaB	N-Ammonium phosphate (p_H 7)	6 months	3.3	3.0

* Table VI clearly shows that the amounts of phosphate and alumina in the ammonium oxalate leachate are nearly equivalent.

Although 58% of the sample (KaA) may be assumed to have reacted with phosphate, no crystallographic evidence of AlPO_4 in the X-ray diffraction pattern has been noticed. Electron diffraction pictures* of KaB, before and after dephosphatisation with *N*-ammonium oxalate solution, have shown definite rings, besides those for kaolinite, corresponding to a new compound which could not be identified in the phosphatised sample; the rings disappeared on dephosphatisation. The dephosphatised mineral was the original kaolinite so far as electron diffraction pattern was concerned.

From the above discussion of the results it is quite clear that phosphate adsorption, or anion exchange, in general, by kaolinites is rendered complicated by the presence of aluminium, either in the free state or present in the laterally broken down lattice. The actual condition can be assessed if the contribution due to aluminium is taken into account. For instance, the very much increased adsorption of phosphate by ground kaolinite has been shown to be due mainly to aluminium, but not to any real increase in the adsorption capacity of kaolinite itself. Accordingly, the phosphate adsorption capacity of kaolinite becomes very low, of the order of 3-4 m.e. per 100 g., which is also the b.e.c. of unground kaolinite. The agreement between the anion exchange or phosphate adsorption capacity of kaolinite and its base exchange capacity has been explained by assuming that the surface OH groups act as the centre of both cation and anion exchange, depending on the experimental conditions (Marshall, "Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals", 1949, Academic Press, N. Y.).

Halloysite

Only a few experiments could be carried out with the halloysite fraction ($< 2\mu$). The results are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Adsorption of ions by halloysite ($< 2\mu$).

Solution.	Adsorption (m.e./100 g.)**
<i>N</i> -Barium acetate (p_H 7)*	4.8 ... (b.e.c.)
<i>N</i> -Ammonium phosphate (p_H 7)	8.2 ... (phosphate)
<i>N</i> -Ammonium phosphate (p_H 4)	15.1 ... (p.a.c.)
<i>N</i> -Ammonium phosphate (p_H 7) †	6.1 ... (phosphate)

* Kindly taken by Prof. R. P. Mitra while at the Imperial College of Science and Technology, London.

** On air-dry sample.

† At 90°-95° for 100 hrs.

The b. e. c. is almost the same as that of kaolinite, but the phosphate adsorption capacity is higher at both p_s 's, particularly in the acidic solution. The influence of temperature is also similar to kaolinite. But halloysite appears to be somewhat more reactive than kaolinite so far as phosphate interaction is concerned. This is possibly due to the comparatively open lattice structure of halloysite.

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